

THE CASE STUDY OF THE EARTH-BUILT WALLS IN THE CIAC, AN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION IN FORTALEZA-CE, BRAZIL

Natalia P. Martins, ETH Zürich, Switzerland, martins@ibi.baug.ethz.ch
(previously: Engineers Without Borders – Joao Pessoa, Brazil)
Anastasija Komkova, ETH Zürich, Switzerland, komkova@ibi.baug.ethz.ch
Gustavo O. V. dos Santos, Macrame Ecologico, Brazil, gvaceli@hotmail.com
Ana Paula Paluszkiewicz, Galpão101, Brazil, galpao101br@gmail.com
Diego Carlos B. Sousa, ECCUS, Brazil, diegoCarlosjp@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

The CIAC (Integrated Center for Community Action, translated from Portuguese) is an educational center designed mainly to promote early childhood education at a densely populated area in the city of Fortaleza-CE, Brazil. The well-documented use of sustainable technologies in the construction of the CIAC, in particular the use of different earthen construction techniques to build non-load-bearing walls, is the subject of this article. The material use and embodied emissions of unfinished walls built using raw earth in rammed earthbags, adobe, and taipa de mão (wattle and daub) were calculated and compared. This study showcases the use of earthen construction techniques in a densely populated urban area and the benefits of the reuse of excavated materials to reduce embodied emissions in earthen construction.

KEYWORDS

Sustainable construction; Rammed earthbag walls; *Taipa de mão* (wattle and daub); Adobe; Embodied emissions; Excavated soil.

INTRODUCTION

The use of sustainable construction techniques in the developing world is an important strategy to limit the effects of climate change. The global south – especially countries located in the in sub-Saharan Africa – will be home for most of the new-coming inhabitants of the planet by the end of the century and also corresponds to the locations where a significant amount of investment and effort towards provision of adequate housing and infrastructure is expected to take place (Wilmoth, Menozzi, & Bassarsky, 2022). Particularly in such locations, redeeming low-carbon construction techniques and materials is an interesting approach to construct new buildings while limiting their environmental impact.

Soil, or raw earth, has been used as building material for thousands of years and in many locations around the globe. It is a versatile minimally-processed material that can be locally-sourced and used in many different earth building techniques. In the last years, earth-based construction techniques have been subject of several studies that highlight the importance of promoting the use of earth materials to reduce the embodied environmental impacts of buildings (Arrigoni, Beckett, Ciancio, & Dotelli, 2017; Ben-Alon, Loftness, Harries, DiPietro, & Hameen, 2019; Cataldo-Born, Araya-Letelier, & Pabón, 2016; Fernandes, Peixoto, Mateus, & Gervásio, 2019; Ismail & Szalay, 2020; Venkatarama Reddy & Jagadish, 2003). When excavated materials are used to replace virgin materials, further environmental benefits that go above the low-carbon construction sphere are identified, such as the reutilization of wastes that would otherwise be landfilled, and minimization of raw material mining (clay, sand). Therefore, the increase in the reuse of excavated soils is also fundamental in order to take steps towards the development of sustainable cities (Hale et al., 2021).

This work aims to present the use of sustainable earthen construction techniques, in particular the use of *taipa de mão*, adobe, and earthbag techniques in the construction of an education center in Brazil, the CIAC, in an attempt to disseminate their use in urban areas. Here, as we present the calculations of material use and carbon emissions from material production for the earth construction techniques used to build the walls in the CIAC, we also discuss the benefits, in terms of environmental impact, of the reuse of excavated materials in buildings. Prior to the presentation and discussion of the results of this study, one whole section is dedicated to describe the CIAC project.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The CIAC (Integrated Center for Community Action, translated from Portuguese) was designed to improve the service offered by a non-profit institution that develops early childhood education programs in Sapiranga, a neighbourhood located in the southeast of the city of Fortaleza, in the northeast region of Brazil (Figure 1). Characterized by a tropical climate, the location has average temperatures of 27.3 °C in the warmest month (November) and 26.2 °C in the coldest month (July). The Sapiranga neighbourhood has over 32 000 inhabitants and is characterized by intense social inequity, population growth, and high rate of violent crimes (Palmeira, 2020).

Figure 1. Location of the CIAC building in the Sapiranga Neighborhood, in Fortaleza, Brazil. Retrieved April 1, 2022 (Google Maps).

After the construction of the CIAC, the institution is able to provide free education, school supplies, and meals in full-time programmes to 96 local children. The new center also supports local families by offering income generation interventions such as professional training courses and workshops on handicraft, music, and dance to the residents of Sapiranga. The CIAC was conceived based on the three pillars of social technologies: low environmental impact, low cost, and easy replication.

A team of architects, engineers and builders experienced in the use of sustainable construction technologies participated in the design, plan, and construction phases of the CIAC. During the construction phase, which started in August 2018 and finished in November 2019, several green technologies were utilized, including the use of earthen construction techniques, an efficient architectural design, and the construction of an evapotranspiration system for onsite wastewater treatment. Workers from the Sapiranga neighborhood were also involved in the construction phase, as preference was given to hire local labor, benefitting local residents. Some of the workers were skilled on earth-based construction techniques such as *taipa de mão*, which was commonly used in rural areas in the country in the past decades. All of the workers and technicians required training on the earthbag technique, which is far less widespread in the area.

Aiming at the dissemination of the easily replicable green technologies used in the project to the general public, a documentary (*Documentário Centro Integrado de Ações Comunitárias - CIAC*, 2021) was developed during the construction phase. The audiovisual production has a character of environmental awareness as it shows the point of view of the professionals and workers who participated in the construction phase. The delivery of workshops to local residents and the production of a booklet for free distribution are other actions that helped disseminate the green technologies implemented in the project.

The next subsections present short descriptions of some of the green technologies used in the project and pictures taken during and after completion of the construction works.

Layout

Having a built-up area 689.04 m² built in a 1720 m² lot, the layout aims to integrate spaces in a fluid, light and functional way, making use of round edges and circular shapes (Figure 2), which are compatible with the construction technique chosen to build the exterior walls. A library and the administration area are located on the front part of the lot, near the classrooms. Bathrooms were built adjacent to the sand and grass playground, located in the central courtyard. The large kitchen area contains areas for inbound delivery, food sanitizing and preparation, storage facilities for monthly, weekly and immediate use, and a circular dining area. Spaces intended for public use were also included in the project, such as a multipurpose hall (geodesic dome), an excavated amphitheatre, a community garden, and a community fridge. Those spaces can be physically isolated from the areas intended for teaching activities.

Figure 2. Layout of the CIAC.

Structure and roof

Wooden structures covered by recycled *Tetra Pack* tiles were used for all areas except for the administration area/library, which was covered by a green roof supported by a reinforced concrete structure. The geodesic dome (Figure 3 (b)) was built using a wooden structure and covered using shingle tiles.

Sanitation systems

A decentralized eco-sanitation solution was developed for the CIAC. Given that the local soil is capable of dealing with wastewater and that sufficient infiltration surface was available, an evapotranspiration system was built onsite to treat wastewaters from bathrooms and toilets (Figure 3 (a)). Greywater i.e., wastewater from non-toilet plumbing systems is treated in infiltration trenches also built onsite. A rainwater harvesting system was built to provide water for the irrigation of a community garden installed in the lot.

Foundations

The foundations were built with stone and crumbling cement mortar, as shown in Figure 3 (c). It is a popular local construction practice due to its low cost and simple execution. On top of the foundations and above the ground level, a second waterproofing layer (40 cm height) was built as a base for the earth-based walls (Figure 3 (d)). This layer consists of a raschel mesh tube, the same used in the earthbag technique, filled with a dry cement paste-poor concrete and hand coated with an asphaltic sealant. It works as an impermeable barrier between the soil and the earthen walls as it prevents capillary rise.

Given the circular shape of the walls in the CIAC, the use of a concrete layer above the ground level would require the production of round shaped formwork. However, since the dry concrete was “cast” inside the raschel mesh tubes, it was possible to speed up the construction and lower material use since the production of round wooden formwork was not required.

Earth-based construction techniques

The use of raw earth construction techniques to build interior partition walls and exterior walls allowed the reuse of excavated materials from the construction site. The soil excavated for the construction of the sanitation systems (evapotranspiration bed and infiltration trenches), the underground water storage tanks (cisterns), the amphitheater, and partially from the foundations – top layer excluded – represents approximately 90% of the nearly 310 m³ of earth materials used for the construction of the walls. In addition to providing immediate use for excavated materials from the construction site, the design choice for earth-based walls was greatly motivated by the desired enhancement in indoor thermal and hygroscopic comfort due to the properties of earth materials (Giuffrida, Caponetto, & Nocera, 2019).

Exterior walls

The exterior walls were built using the rammed earthbag technique, which consists in filling woven polyethylene or polypropylene bags with earth materials, stacking, and compacting them to form walls (J. Kennedy, 2002), as shown in Figure 3 (h). In the CIAC, *raschel* - or polypropylene mesh rolls - were used in combination with excavated materials from the site. Earthbag joints between layers were enabled by the meshed nature of polypropylene rolls used. The commonly used barbed wire, which was found to have irrelevant contribution to the structural safety of straight superadobe walls (Canadell, Blanco, & Cavalaro, 2016) was therefore not utilized between layers.

Soil in a mix ratio of 25-30% stable clay to 70-75% well-graded sand and gravel of up to 2.5 cm in size, with an average moisture content of 10-12% depending on the type of soil, is recommended for use as fill material in the bags (Wesonga, Kasedde, Kibwami, & Manga, 2021). The excavated soil from the construction site presented the fractions of fine and coarse particles close to the ones considered ideal for earth construction using the earthbag technique, except for a higher clay content. High clay contents in soils can lead to cracks on the earth walls due to the shrinking behaviour of clays. That resulted in the occurrence of cracks on the first layers of compacted earthbags. To prevent the propagation of the cracks on the subsequent layers, a waiting time was inserted before the build-up of the next layer. That did not impair the productivity since the construction of walls was being carried out at several sites i.e., individual classrooms, simultaneously.

No additional granulometric correction was done on the soil. Moreover, since the topsoil, which is often rich in organic matter, was not used, and the presence of plant roots and oversized gravel in the deeper layers was not substantial, no additional sieving was performed. Purchased materials (sand and clay) were also used to supplement the production of exterior walls because the amount of excavated materials from the site was insufficient. The purchased materials presented overall good quality and did not demand sieving prior to their use.

Interior partition walls

The interior partition walls between the classrooms and one of the walls of the library were made using *taipa de mão*, also known as *pau-a-pique*. That is a colonial raw earth construction technique inherited from the Portuguese colonial settlers, and possibly adapted to include contributions from African and Indigenous people (Olender, 2006). The set up used in the CIAC consists of a single lightweight wood frame structure (Figure 2 (e)) filled with a mixture of mud and natural fibers (8cm length) (Figure 2 (f)). Prior to their use in the mix design, the grading of excavated materials was corrected by the addition of purchased sand due to their original high clay content.

Adobe, which consists of a unfired brick produced with mud and straw molded into wooden molds, was casted and dried onsite (Figure 2 (g)) and later used in the construction of one of the walls of the library and on the wall of the administration area. For the production of the mud, the grading of the excavated material was corrected by adding purchased sand.

Figure 3. (a) Evapotranspiration system (under construction); (b) Assembly of the geodesic dome; (c) Foundations (under construction); (d) First layers of coated earthbags filled with a cement paste-poor concrete; (e) Construction of interior walls using lightweight wooden frames to be filled with a mixture of soil and straw (*taipa de mão*); (f) *Taipa de mão*; (g) Drying of adobe blocks used to build interior walls; (h) Ramming of exterior earthbag walls; (i) Finishing of exterior walls; (j) Aerial view after completion of construction works. Pictures taken by Andre Souza, 2018-2019.

Plaster, render, and finishing

To achieve a flat surface, renders and plasters were applied to exterior walls, as well as a natural paint finish. The render used on the exterior walls of the CIAC and the plaster applied to interior walls of the classrooms was a mixture of earth, straw, sand, and lime. A second layer of an earth, sand, and lime mixture was applied to both plasters and renders to give a finer finishing. Last, an earth-based paint made with earth, mineral pigment (iron oxide), cassava starch adhesive, and water was used to paint interior walls. The exterior walls received a layer of paint made with earth, mineral pigment (iron oxide), PVA-based glue, and water (Figure 3 (i)).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analyses of material use and carbon emissions from material production of the different earthen walls built in the CIAC: *taipa de mão* walls, adobe walls, and rammed earthbag walls. Based on the quantification of materials used to build the interior partition walls (adobe and *taipa de mão*) and exterior walls (earthbag with raschel mesh tubing) of the building, we show in Figure 4 the distribution of material use and the embodied CO₂ emissions of the unfinished earth-based walls considering two scenarios: (1) assuming the utilization of virgin (purchased) materials locally sourced, and (2) assuming the reuse of materials available onsite or near-site *e.g.*, excavated soil, dismantled pallets.

The carbon emissions are given in terms of the global warming potential (GWP) in kg CO_{2-eq}/m² of wall, calculated using IPCC 2013 impact assessment method, where life cycle inventory was collected through Ecoinvent v3.8 database. No carbon emissions from material production were assigned to the reused and waste materials; the avoided emissions from treatment of inert waste in landfills were plotted as negative emissions to illustrate additional carbon savings related to avoidance of waste disposal. A functional unit of 1 m² of wall used to enable the comparison between techniques. The system boundaries focus on material production. It must also be noted that no stabilizers *i.e.*, cement, lime were added to earth mixtures. The detailed description of the labels used in the techniques/scenarios is given in Table 1.

Given the larger thickness required by the rammed earthbag walls and the densely compacted state of earth materials after ramming, a larger mass of materials, approximately 767 kg, is required to build a 1m² wall using this technique. The *taipa* technique is the least consuming in terms of material use, demanding the utilization of 131 kg of materials per m² of wall, including also wood and straw. Despite being more demanding in terms of material use, the utilization of rammed earthbags in the CIAC enabled the easy construction of the circular walls proposed in the architectural design while consuming the large volumes of excavated materials generated on the site due to the construction of the sanitation

systems. Moreover, this technique showed to be less sensitive to changes in material grading and quality than *taipa de mão* or adobe, therefore the addition of purchased materials aimed at grading correction was not required. For the production of the adobe blocks and the *taipa de mão* mud, however, the excavated soil demanded grading correction with purchased sand.

Figure 4. Diagram presenting the mass of materials used/m² of wall for earthbag, *taipa de mão*, and adobe techniques. The areas of the circles are proportional to the total mass of materials used. Below, the calculated carbon footprint is shown considered two scenarios: (1) assuming the utilization of virgin (purchased) materials, and (2) assuming the reuse of materials e.g., excavated soil, dismantled pallets.

Table 1. Description of the labels used to designate the earth-based techniques in the different scenarios.

Label	Description
Earthbag virgin	1 m ² wall built using the earthbag technique (35 cm thickness). Virgin materials locally sourced (sand, clay, polypropylene woven mesh bags) were used in the mix design.
Earthbag excavated	1 m ² wall built using the earthbag technique (35 cm thickness). Excavated materials collected onsite were used to replace locally sourced virgin materials (clay, sand) in the mix design.
Taipa virgin	1 m ² wall built using the <i>taipa de mão</i> technique (12 cm thickness). Locally sourced virgin materials (sand, clay, wood, straw) were used in the mix design.
Taipa reused	1 m ² wall built using the <i>taipa de mão</i> technique (12 cm thickness). Excavated materials collected onsite were used to replace locally sourced virgin clay and sand. Soil grading correction (by adding 20% virgin sand) was considered. Reused pallets available near-site replaced virgin wood in the mix design.
Adobe virgin	1 m ² wall built using the adobe (12x15x40 cm) technique; 1.5 cm thick adobe mortar included. Locally sourced virgin materials (sand, clay, straw) were used in the mix design.
Adobe excavated	1 m ² wall built using the adobe (12x15x40 cm) technique; 1.5 cm thick adobe mortar included. Excavated materials collected onsite were used to replace locally sourced virgin clay and sand in the mix design. Soil grading correction (by adding 50% virgin sand) was considered.

Considering the use of virgin materials (scenario 1), the earthbag wall displayed a considerably higher carbon footprint than *taipa de mão* and adobe walls, which is not surprising given the higher material demand of this technique. The value obtained in this study, 55 kg CO_{2-eq}/m², is not directly comparable to values from the literature for earthbag social houses in Chile (Cataldo-Born et al., 2016) and Sudan (Ismail & Szalay, 2020), which are around 250 kg CO₂/earthbag habitable m², because the previous studies take into account other elements in addition to the walls, such as foundations, structure etc., and they used cement-stabilized earth materials in the calculations. In those studies, the authors highlight that the use of industrialized materials such as cement is responsible for most of the CO₂ emissions. Additionally, houses built using the earthbag technique showed a superior performance – compared to brick masonry houses – also in terms of energy savings, initial investment, and life cycle cost (Cataldo-Born et al., 2016; Wesonga et al., 2021).

For all techniques, the largest fraction of CO_{2-eq} emissions come from the production of clay. Considering that the earth materials are obtained from onsite excavations (scenario 2), which took place in the CIAC, a considerable drop in the carbon footprint is observed for the three techniques; the calculated CO_{2-eq} emissions reach values below 1 kg CO_{2-eq} per 1m² of wall. Only emissions associated with production of polypropylene textile used for industrial bags is contributing to the carbon footprint of the earthbag wall. It must be noted, however, that the actual carbon footprint may be slightly higher because the weaving process was not taken into account when calculating the embodied emissions of the polypropylene bags. The emissions from the *taipa de mão* walls become nearly zero, even considering grading correction with purchased sand. Moreover, even requiring more intense grading correction of the excavated soil, the adobe wall still has an extremely low carbon footprint.

These results show that the use of excavated materials from the construction site has a significant effect on the reduction of the carbon footprint of walls built using different earthen construction techniques, where reduction is 91-98% . Despite having originally low emissions compared to conventional burnt bricks masonry, a striking additional benefit can be reached even in cases where grading correction of soil is required. Moreover, when excavated materials are used to replace virgin materials, the environmental benefit is evident even when more material demanding techniques, i.e., rammed earthbag, are utilized.

CONCLUSIONS

This study showcases the use of earthen techniques in the construction of a community center in an urban area in Brazil and the benefits of the reuse of excavated materials to reduce embodied emissions in earthen construction. The intense reutilization of excavated materials from the construction site was enabled by efficient engineering and architectural choices made at the design phase, which coupled the provision of excavated sanitation solutions with the reuse of the excavated soil to build exterior and interior partition walls. It was shown that the environmental performance - in terms of emitted carbon from material production - of already low-carbon earth-based walls can be further enhanced by 91-98% if excavated materials from the site are utilized to replace virgin materials, since most of the CO₂ emissions come from the mining and processing of virgin clay and sand. Furthermore, by using excavated earth in construction, we can avoid emissions associated with its disposal in landfills.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The residents of the Sapiranga community, professionals and workers engaged in the design, construction, and operation of the CIAC are greatly acknowledged for their collective effort to materialize this project.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.

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